

EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING IN COMMUNICATIVE CONTROL AND PERSONAL ADAPTIVE POTENTIAL OF FUTURE GENERAL PRACTITIONERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055331>

Introduction. Today, the problem of ensuring the professional health and personal peace of mind of doctors all over the world is of paramount importance. The mental, emotional and stressful state of a doctor is important in medical practice, and the complications of this stress lead to a number of shortcomings in the practice of doctors. Specialists from various industries are trying to give meaning to the very concept of a general practitioner and, on this basis, to determine its main functions, problematic aspects. However, as practice shows, there is a lack of a unified approach to this problem [1,2,3,4,6]

Purpose of the study: To reveal the dynamics of the level of manifestation of communicative control and personal adaptive potential in future general practitioners before and after the training program.

Material and methods of research: For the purposes of the study, the dynamics of the level of manifestation of communicative control and personal adaptive potential in future general practitioners was revealed, an empirical study was organized and conducted, in which 97 future general practitioners of the third, fourth and fifth year of study took part, as female as well as male. To achieve the goal, the test questionnaire of communicative control by M. Schneider and the multi-level personal questionnaire "Adaptiveness" by A.G. Maklakov, S.V. Chermynanin were allowed.

Result and discussion. The analysis of the results of the psychodiagnostic examination showed that, following the results of the training program, the future general practitioners of the experimental group (n=97) significantly improved the severity of the previously identified complex of individual psychological characteristics interpreted as a group of personal determinants of professional stress. The number of future general practitioners with a low level of situational anxiety (diagnosed using the Anxiety Research Test by Ch.D. Spielberger and Yu.L. Khanin) increased from 6.1% (6 people - before the training program) to 19, 4% (19 people - after the training program). With an average level, it slightly increased, from 72.4% (71 people grams of training sessions) up to 76.5% (75 people - after the program of training sessions). Accordingly, with a high level of situational anxiety, it significantly decreased from 21.4% (21 people - before the training program) to 4.1% (4 people - after the training program), (See Figure 10).

At the same time, such positive dynamics was not observed among future general practitioners who were not involved in the prepared training program. So, in the respondents of the control group (n=97), the level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress (diagnosed using the Questionnaire for determining neuropsychic stress by T.A. Nemchin) remained practically without significant changes:

low level of neuropsychic stress: before the training program - 10.3% (10 people), after the training program - 10.3% (10 people); average level of neuropsychic stress: before the training program - 39.2% (38 people), after the training program - 38.1% (37 people); high level of neuropsychic stress: before the training program - 50.5% (49 people), after the training program - 51.5% (50 people).

Rice. 10. Dynamics of the level of manifestation of situational anxiety of future general practitioners of the experimental group before and after the training program (n=98).

The level of communicative control (diagnosed using M. Schneider's Communication Control Test Questionnaire) also did not undergo significant changes in the control group (n=97): low level of communicative control: before the training program - 36.1% (35 people), after the program of training sessions - 36.1% (35 people); the average level of communicative control: before the training program - 55.7% (54 people), after the training program - 56.7% (55 people); high level of communicative control: before the training program - 8.2% (8 people), after the training program - 7.2% (7 people).

The level of adaptive potential (diagnosed using the Multilevel Personality Questionnaire "Adaptiveness" by A.G. Maklakov, S.V. Chermyanin) among the respondents of the control group (n=97) remained without significant changes: low level of adaptive potential: before the training program - 8.2% (8 people), after the training program - 9.3% (9

people); average level of adaptive potential: before the training program - 83.5% (81 people), after the training program - 82.5% (80 people); high level of adaptive potential: before the training program - 8.2% (8 people), after the training program - 8.2% (8 people).

The communicative features of the respondents in the control group (diagnosed using the Multilevel Personality Questionnaire "Adaptiveness" by A.G. Maklakov, S.V. Chermyanin) did not undergo significant changes: below the average level of manifestation of communicative features: before the training program - 14.4% (14 people), after the training program - 15.5% (15 people); the average level of manifestation of communicative features: before the training program - 75.3% (73 people), after the training program - 80.4% (78 people); a high level of manifestation of communicative features: before the training program - 10.3% (10 people), after the training program - 4.1% (4 people).

The level of anxiety (diagnosed using the Anxiety Research Test by Ch.D. Spielberger and Yu.L. Khanin) also did not change significantly in the control group. Thus, the manifestations of situational anxiety at: a low level before the training program was 6.2% (6 people), and after the training program was 7.2% (7 people); the average level before the training program was 75.3% (73 people), and after the training program was 71.1% (69 people); a high level before the training program was 18.6% (18 people), and after the training program was 21.6% (21 people).

Manifestations of personal anxiety at: a low level before the training program was 11.3% (11 people), and after the training program was 11.3% (11 people); the average level before the training program was 84.5% (82 people), and after the training program was 82.5% (80 people); a high level before the training program was 4.1% (4 people), and after the training program was 6.2% (6 people).

Comparative analysis of the first and second psychodiagnostic examinations using the test questionnaire of stress resistance by S. Cohen and G. Williamson revealed the positive impact of the prepared training sessions on the stress resistance of future general practitioners (See Figure 11).

So, as a result of the program impact, the number of respondents in the experimental group (n=98): with a low level of stress resistance decreased from 17.3% (17 people) to 2% (2 people); with a lower average level of stress resistance decreased from 24.5% (24 people) to 3.1% (3 people); with an average level of stress resistance decreased from 51% (50 people) to 37.8% (37 people); with an above average level of stress resistance increased significantly from 4.1% (4 people) to 46.9% (46 people); with a high level of stress resistance increased significantly from 3.1% (3 people) to 10.2% (10 people).

In the control group (n=97), no such changes were observed. The number of future general practitioners: with a low level of stress resistance remained practically without significant changes (before the training program - 14.4%, 14 people, after the training program - 13.4%, 13 people); with a lower average level of stress tolerance remained unchanged (before the training program - 19.6%, 19 people, after the training program - 19.6%, 19 people); with an average level of stress resistance remained without significant changes (before the training program - 52.6%, 51 people, after the training program - 51.5%, 50 people); with an above average level of stress tolerance, there were no significant changes (before the training program - 7.2%, 7 people, after the training program - 8.2%, 8 people); with a high level of stress resistance remained without significant changes (before the training program - 6.2%, 6 people, after the training program - 7.2%, 7 people).

All of the above comparative psychodiagnostic data before and after the training program is confirmed and statistically according to the results of the analysis of the equality of the average values in the experimental and control groups according to Student's t-test.

Rice. Fig. 11. Dynamics of the level of stress resistance of future general practitioners of the comparison groups before and after the training program (n=97).

Conclusion: As a result, future general practitioners have increased communicative control, decreased the level of adaptive potential, increased significantly, and also significantly increased their resistance to stress.

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